
Bradford's law of Scattering Revisited: A study based on the References in Doctoral theses in the area of Physics

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A study of the five years data of journals cited by the physicists at the University of Kerala (UoK), India has been carried out to examine the applicability of Bradford's law of scattering on a sample of 303 journals containing 2655 citations collected from 12 doctoral theses during the period 2004-08. Ranked list of journals are prepared, and the most preferred journal is Journal of Geophysical Research with the highest of 345 (12.97%) citations. The paper provides summary and review of the scholarly contribution on the various facets of Bradford's law. In addition to the theoretical aspects of the law, the review covers papers dealing with the application of the law in the various subject fields.

Applicability of Bradford's law on various methods has been tested. The journal distribution pattern of the doctoral theses does not confirm the Bradford's distribution pattern. The Bradford multipliers are calculated, and the law was found to be applicable with the value of k as 2.66. The distribution of the journals in three zones done and the number of references in each zone is then calculated. The applicability of Leimkuhler model is also tested with the present data. The Bradford's law of scattering doesn't follow the journal distribution pattern.

1. Introduction

Classifying and counting scientists, books, papers and citations, as early statistical bibliographer set out to do, remain a fairly extemporary activity as long as data continued to be examined outside a mathematical framework that would let them disclose meaningful patterns in the documentation process. The turning point occurred between the 1920s and the 1930s, when three basic bibliometric studies were published: Lotka's work on the distribution of scientific papers among authors; Bradford's contribution on the scattering of papers on a given subject in scientific journals; and Zipf's work on the distribution of words in text (De Bellis [1]).

Citation analysis techniques are one of the important techniques among other informetric techniques for finding out the important journals in a particular field and are becoming popular in their practical applications in libraries and information centers. Journals are the carriers of the latest information and are much sought after other documents by researchers. Journal literature is an important source of information for latest developments in the area of a research. All new concepts, principles, laws, etc. are reported in journals and the subject matter of an article is more in depth, complex and propagates new knowledge to the existing stock.

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The rank list is essentially a practical tool designed to help the librarians and research scientists to select the journals of maximum utility in relation to their coverage of new and important literature in a particular subject area.

The concept of 'core journals' is being derived from Bradford's law of scattering, which was formulated by Samuel Clement Bradford in 1934 [2]. Bradford first published his observation of the increasing scatter of relevant journal articles on a given topic and later in 1948 [3], summarised these observations by relating the number of journals in the nuclear, or most productive zone to the number of journals in successively less productive zones containing equal numbers of papers. One of the areas in bibliometric research concerns the application of most commonly used bibliometric laws such as Bradford's law of Scattering. Among the several statistical expressions, Bradford's law of scattering is perhaps the most popular and the best known of all the bibliometric concepts that try to describe the effective working of science by mathematical means [4].

2. Previous studies

S. C. Bradford (1934, 1948) studied the inverse relationship between the number of articles published in a subject area and the number of journals in which the articles appear is referred to as journal productivity. Bradford's law of scattering has been the main topic of many articles in LIS literature. The discussions of the law take several directions: analysis of the law itself, attempts to refine it, comparison with other laws, and its applications.

Numerous formulations of the law have been proposed. The first notable paper on the law was that of Vickery [5] and the next paper of Kendall [6]. The 'bipolar' nature of the law was further discussed by Wilkinson [7], who suggested that the verbal formulation of the law expressed Bradford's theory, while the graphical formulation expressed his observations. The search for an exact formulation of Bradford's law stated by Vickery and Leimkuhler [8] and was further pursued by many other authors. In 1977, Brookes [9] contributed his 'theory of Bradford's law' to the commemorative issue of the *Journal of Documentation*. In this classic paper, Brookes did a complete evaluation of the Bradford law and concluded that 'Bradford was therefore a pioneer in social mathematics'. Avramescu [10] gave the theoretical foundation of the law. A comprehensive review of the mathematical evolution of Bradford's law was done by Oluic-Vukovic [11] and Locket [12] who reviewed some significant studies. An empirical examination of the law was done by Qiu [13]. The gap between empirical and theoretical considerations of the phenomenon described by Bradford's law has been pointed out by Drott [14].

Different authors gave many alternative models for scattering. Groos [15] observed a S-shaped curve (with a droop, at the end of the curve) to explain law of scattering. Fairthorne [16] and also Asai [17] suggested a log model. The dual of Bradford' law was proposed by Egghe [18]. Burrell [19] suggested warring process to explain general features of Bradford' law. Basu [20] suggested that the Bradford' regularity acquires two pairs of description, Bradford's verbal law (sequence of ratios) and the classic Leimkuhler law (equation); Bradford's graphical law (plotted graphs) and Brooke' law (equation). Again she suggested a model to explain distribution of articles in journals based on probabilistic considerations [21].

The theory of Bradford's law to the calculation of Leimkuhler law was proposed by Egghe [22] and he has also given a note on different Bradford multipliers [23]. To identify a suitable model to explain the law of scattering, Ravichandra Rao [24] fitted about 24 different models to the 12 different sets of data. He observed that log- normal model fit much better than other models, including the log- linear model. Wagner-Dobber [25] has also made their comments on the law. Recently, Nicolaisen and Hjørland [26] in their article presented practical potentials of Bradford' law.

The extension of Bradford's law from one to several disciplines has been put in the form of a law by Eugene Garfield [27]. He talked about the number of journals involved in publishing the literature of a single field. Garfield's law of concentration states that "a basic concentration of journals I the common core or nucleus of all fields". An extension of Bradford's law was proposed by Sengupta. It states that "during the phases of rapid growth of knowledge in a scientific discipline, articles of interest to that discipline appear in increasing number of periodicals distant from that field" [28].

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There has been considerable research conducted on the empirical validation of Bradford's law. Although many studies have confirmed the validity of the law, they often found that the value of the Bradford multiplier varies among subjects categories. On the application side, the studies of Sengupta [29] and Goffman and Morris [30] are significant. The applicability of the two vital formulations (verbal and graphical) of Bradford's law of Scattering was tested by Arjun Lal and Panda [31]. The data were collected from 20 doctoral theses in plant Pathology submitted to Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar, during 1980-93. Gupta [32] studied the applicability of Bradford's law to citation data in Ethiopian medical journal. Other studies include, Lawani [33] in Agriculture, Tyagi [34] in Physics, Nweke [35] in Zoology, Asundi and Kabir [36] in Horticulture, Bandyopadhyay [37] in different disciplines, Shukla and Saksena [38] in Bio energy, Gupta and Kumar [39] in theoretical population genetics.

The law is applied to study not only the scattering of publications, but in other spheres also. A study conducted by Garg and Sharma [40] of R & D indicators in Indian industry using Bradford's law bears testimony to this fact.

Many scholars have studied the application of Bradford's law in the distribution of publications in journals, coverage in international indexing and abstracting services etc., but few have analysed the applicability of Bradford's law in the distribution of journal citations in a particular institution. Hence this study on the journals cited by the physicists of the University of Kerala (UoK) in their doctoral theses becomes significant.

2.1. *The University of Kerala*

The University of Travancore was established in 1937 by a royal proclamation by His Highness Shri. Bala Rama Varma, Maharaja of Travancore, to promote technological education in the state, to encourage original research in various branches of applied sciences and to provide education to all classes of people for the conservation and advancement of the arts and culture of Kerala. The University of Kerala is the first of the five universities to be established in the modern State of Kerala, the third in the erstwhile princely India of the British days and the sixteenth in the country as a whole [41].

The Department of Physics was formally established in August 1970. Earlier the department was at Cochin and when the Cochin University of Science and Technology (CUSAT) was formed in 1970, a new department started at the Kariavattom Campus, Thiruvananthapuram. Ph. D programme has been in operation since the inception of the department. More than 100 students of the department have been awarded Ph. D since 1971. The major thrust areas within the subject in which research activities are being actively pursued are: Space Physics, Materials Science, Spectroscopy, Geophysics and Non linear Optical science.

3. Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study are:

- (i) To prepare a rank list of most cited journals by UoK physicists.
- (ii) To study the phenomenon of scattering for journal citations.
- (iii) To test the validity of verbal and graphical formulation of Bradford's law of scattering.

4. Methodology

A total of 303 journals containing 2,655 references collected from 12 doctoral theses are arranged in their descending order of productivity. The study treats references as items and journals as source. The verbal formulation was tested by three separate parameters for carrying the different number of periodicals, while for testing the appropriateness of graphical formulation, the natural log value of the cumulative number of journals were calculated for plotting the graph.

4.1. *Bradford's Law of Scattering*

Samuel Clement Bradford, a chemist turned librarian was interested in the problem of the scatter of papers on a scientific subject through the scientific journals. Bradford's law of scattering describes a quantitative relation between journals and the papers they publish. Bradford, chief librarian at the London Science Museum, has made a statistical analysis of two geophysics bibliographies, the Current Bibliography of Applied Geophysics (1928-1931) and the Quarterly Bibliography of Lubrication (1931-1933) [2]. He tested the journals containing references to these fields in their descending order of productivity and then divided the articles into three approximately equal zones or groups. He termed the first one as the nuclear zone, which is highly productive; the second zone as moderately productive zone; and the third he described as peripheral zone or low productive zone. Bradford has discovered regularity in calculating the number of titles in each of the three zones.

On the basis of the observations, Bradford concluded that the ratio of the titles of journals in successive zones followed a common pattern. Bradford's verbal formulation stated that "if scientific journals are arranged in order of their decreasing productivity of articles on a given subject, they may be divided into a nucleus of periodicals more particularly devoted to the subject, and several 'group' or 'zones' containing the same number of articles as the nucleus, where the number of periodicals in the nucleus and succeeding zones will be $1:n:n^2$, 'n' is a multiplier"[3].

Based on Bradford's observations, Brookes [42] suggested the following linear relation to describe the scattering phenomenon as:

$$F(x) = a + b \log x$$

Where $F(x)$ is the cumulative number of reference contained in the first x most productive journals; a and b are constants. This is the most widely used formulation of Bradford's law.

Vickery [5] extended the verbal formulation to show that it can be applied to any number of zones of equal yield. Leimkuhler [8] issued a simple function for Bradford's distribution, which was named after him:

$$R(x) = a \log(1 + bx)$$

Where $R(r)$ is the cumulative number of article contributed by journals ranked 1 through r , and a and b are parameters.

Similarly, Brookes derivation for journal productivity takes the form $R(r) = a \log(b/r)$

Further, Wilkinson [7] noticed that the formulae provided by Leimkuhler and Brookes did not really describe the same phenomenon.

Starting from the late 1960s, several mathematical formulations, models, and syntheses of previous statements related to Bradford's law have been put forth, but very little agreement exists about which model is the best. Brookes expression of the Bradford distribution has however gained wide acceptance.

4.2. *Theoretical aspects of Bradford's law*

Bradford's law of scattering describes a quantitative relationship between journals and the papers they publish. It explains that, only a small number of core journals will be need to supply the nucleus of papers on a given topic which accounts for a substantial percentage (1/3) of the articles, to be followed by a second larger group of journals that accounts for another third, while a much larger group of journals picked up the last third [3].

There are two most widely recognised formulations of the Bradford's law: the verbal formulation which is derived from the verbal statement of Bradford's conclusion, and the graphical formulation, which is an empirical expression derived from the graphical survey of a distribution of periodicals [43].

Bradford did not give a mathematical model for his law. Models were suggested later by Brookes, Vickery and Leimkuhler.

Several authors, while explaining the scattering of articles in journals, have formulated many different models of Bradford's law. Leimkuhler developed a model based on Bradford's verbal formulation as [44]:

$$\begin{aligned} R(r) &= a \log(1 + br) \\ r &= 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

while explaining Leimkuhler's law, Egghe shows that

$$a = Y_0 / \log k \quad (2)$$

$$b = k - 1/r_0 \quad (3)$$

Here r_0 – is the number of sources in the first Bradford group.

Y_0 – the number of items in every Bradford group (all these group of item being of equal sizes), and

k – the Bradford multiplier.

$R(r)$ is the cumulative number of items produced by the sources of rank $1, 2, 3, \dots, r$ a and b are constants appearing in the law of Leimkuhler.

In forming Bradford groups, it is shown that the number of groups p is a parameter that can be chosen freely.

Egghe [22] has shown the mathematical formula for calculating the Bradford Multiplier k as

$$k = (e^\gamma y_m)^{1/p} \quad (4)$$

Where γ is Euler's number ($e^\gamma = 1.781$).

If the sources are ranked in decreasing order of productivity, then y_m is the number of items in the most productivity sources.

Then y_0 and r_0 as follows

$$Y_0 = y_m^2 \log k \text{ and} \quad (5)$$

$$r_0 = (k - 1)Y_m \quad (6)$$

Once p is chosen, the value of k can be calculated by using

$$k = (1.781 y_m)^{1/p} \quad (7)$$

and $Y_0 = A/P$

Where A denotes the total number of articles.

Let T denote the total number of journals in Bradford group, there are $r_0 k^{i-1}$ sources ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, p$)

$$T = r_0 + r_0 k + r_0 k^2 + \dots + r_0 k^{p-2} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{So, } r_0 = T / (1 + k + k^2 + \dots + k^{p-1}) = T(k - 1) / (k^p - 1) \quad (9)$$

Since A and T are known from the data set, r_0 and Y_0 are calculated, once p is calculated by the formula (7).

Gupta and Kumar [39] have given the theoretical aspects of Bradford's law and they studied its applicability using the above method. According to Brookes [45], to test the conformity of Bradford's law, one should meet three implicit conditions.

- (i) In dividing the journals in to zones, the number of articles in each zone must remain constant
- (ii) The Bradford multiplier k must be greater than one.
- (iii) The Bradford multiplier must remain approximately constant.

5. Analysis and discussion

5.1. Top ranked journals

Core journals ranking studies are usually made to help in the selection of journals and in assessing the importance of one or more journals in a particular subject field.

The journals are arranged in their respective descending order of frequency and in alphabetical order among the same rank number. The journal contributing the largest number of articles is ranked as number one, next as ranked two and so on. The criterion for ranking is purely quantitative not qualitative.

The ranked list of most cited journals of UoK are shown in the Table 1.

The analysis shows that the Physics literature are scattered in 303 journals accounting 2665 citations. Of the 303 journals cited in University of Kerala theses 54 are cited at least 10 times or more. In the rank list, the J. Geophys. Res. published by American Geophysical Union top the list with the highest contribution of 345 (12.97%) citations followed by Spectrochim Acta A, with a share of 116 citations (4.36%). J.Atmos.Solar-Terr. Phys occupies the third place with 95 citations (3.57%). The remarkable feature of the study is the high status of subject journals in the core journal list.

Table 1
Core journals with the number of Publications

Sl.No.	Journals	Country	Publisher	Rank	Count	%
1	J.Geophys.Res.	USA	AGU	1	345	12.97
2	Spectrochim. Acta A	UK	Pergamon	2	116	4.36
3	J. Atmos.Sol.Terr. Phys	UK	Pergamon	3	95	3.57
4	Geophys.Res.Lett.	USA	AGU	4	90	3.38
5	J.Raman Spectrosc.	Netherlands	John Wiley	5	78	2.93
6	Phys.Fluids	USA	AIP	6	67	2.52
7	Thin Solid films	Netherlands	Elsevier	7	64	2.41
8	Phys.Plasmas	USA	AIP	8	50	1.88
9	Ind.J.Rad.&Sp. Phys.	India	CSIR	9	49	1.84
10	J.Solid State Chem.	USA	Academic	9	49	1.84
11	J. Appl. Phys.	USA	AIP	10	48	1.80
12	J.Mater.Sci.	Netherlands	Springer	11	46	1.73
13	J.Chem.Phys.	USA	AIP	12	45	1.69
13	Phys. Rev. Lett.	USA	APS	12	45	1.69
14	Solar Phys.	Netherlands	Springer	12	45	1.69
15	J.Mol.Struct.	Netherlands	Elsevier	13	44	1.65
16	Phys.Rev.B	USA	APS	14	40	1.50
17	Ann.Geophysicae	Germany	EGU	15	37	1.39
18	J.Phys.Chem.Solids	USA	Pergamon	15	37	1.39
19	Am.Ceram.Soc.Bull.	USA	ACS	16	36	1.35
20	J.Am.Ceram.Soc	USA	ACS	17	35	1.32
21	Planet Space Sci.	USA	Pergamon	18	33	1.24
22	Plas. Phys.Contr.Fus.	UK	IOP	18	33	1.24
23	Nature	UK	Nature Pub.	19	32	1.20
24	Phys. Rev.	USA	APS	19	32	1.20
25	J. Am. Chem. Soc	USA	ACS	20	31	1.17

5.2. Application of Bradford's law

In order to observe the appropriateness of the distribution of journals using the verbal formulation of Bradford law, the following explanations are made and the results are presented. The first part deals with the verbal formulation of the theory based on data consisting whole periodical references, arranged by their decreasing frequency of citations while the second part examines the graphical representations based on the same data.

5.2.1. Verbal formulation

To test the verbal formulation of Bradford's law, the Table 2 is prepared with several details of journal citations. The number of cited journals are arranged by decreasing number of citations. The rank, number of journals, number of citations, cumulative citations, log of cumulative citations are given in the Table 2.

Bradford's technique is used to group the journals in to three major zones of productivity and 'Bradford's law of scattering', as discussed above, is applied to test the appropriateness of verbal formulation.

The frequency of citations arranged from the highest to lowest are presented in the Table 2 with the corresponding number of journal titles having that frequency and the rank occupied by the titles. In the successive columns of the Table 2, the cumulative number and percentage of journal per rank and corresponding references in number and percentage along with the log (n) are also reflected.

In this study, 8 journals covered 905 articles, next 23 journals covered 851 articles and the next 272 journals covered 899 articles. In other words 8 journals covered one third of the total citations, the next 23 journals accounted for another one third citations and the next 272 journals covered remaining one third.

The distribution of journals and corresponding number of citations in the three zones along with the value of Bradford multiplier are shown in the Table 3.

Thus the first zone or nucleus contains eight journals, followed by second zone containing 23 journals and third zone having 272 journals. According to Bradford, the zones, thus identified will form an approximately geometric series in the form 8 : 23 : 272.

$$\text{But here, } 23 = 8 \times 2.88 \text{ and } 272 \approx 8 \times 2.88^2 \times 4$$

According to Bradford, the relationship between the zones is $1 : n : n^2$, while the relationship of each zones in the present study is 8 : 23 : 272 which does not fit into the Bradford's distribution.

Therefore the Bradford's formulation may be modified in the following way to suit the present journal distribution pattern as:

$$8 : 8 \times 2.88 : 8 \times 2.88^2 \times 4$$

Substituting $2.88 = n$, then

$$8 : 8n : 8n^2 \times 4 \approx 1 : n : 4n^2$$

Where, 8 represent the number of journals in the nucleus and $n = 2.88$ is a multiplier. Thus, the modified Bradford's law of scattering is testified. But here the multiplier calculated is for the first two zones, and for the third zone its value is found to be 4 fold.

The mean value multiplier is 7.36.

Therefore $8 : 8 \times 7.36 : 8 \times 7.36^2 :: 1 : n : n^2$

$$8 : 58.88 : 433.36 \approx 500.24$$

$$\text{The percentage of error} = \frac{500.24 - 303}{303} \times 100 = 65.09\%$$

Here the percentage of error is high, and the present data will not confirm the Bradford's law.

Table 2
Citations and Citing Journals used by Researchers of UoK

Rank	No. of Journals	Cum. No. Journals	No. of Citations	Total No. of Citations	Cum. No. of Citations	log (n)	% of Citations	% of Total Journals
1	1	1	345	345	345	0.00	12.99	0.33
2	1	2	116	116	461	0.69	17.36	0.66
3	1	3	95	95	556	1.10	20.94	0.99
4	1	4	90	90	646	1.39	24.33	1.32
5	1	5	78	78	724	1.61	27.27	1.65
6	1	6	67	67	791	1.79	29.79	1.98
7	1	7	64	64	855	1.95	32.20	2.31
8	1	8	50	50	905	2.08	34.09	2.64
9	2	10	49	98	1003	2.30	37.78	3.30
10	1	11	48	48	1051	2.40	39.59	3.63
11	1	12	46	46	1097	2.48	41.32	3.96
12	3	15	45	135	1232	2.71	46.40	4.95
13	1	16	44	44	1276	2.77	48.06	5.28
14	1	17	40	40	1316	2.83	49.57	5.61
15	2	19	37	74	1390	2.94	52.35	6.27
16	1	20	36	36	1426	3.00	53.71	6.60
17	1	21	35	35	1461	3.04	55.03	6.93
18	2	23	33	66	1527	3.14	57.51	7.59
19	2	25	32	64	1591	3.22	59.92	8.25
20	1	26	31	31	1622	3.26	61.09	8.58
21	1	27	29	29	1651	3.30	62.18	8.91
22	1	28	28	28	1679	3.33	63.24	9.24
23	2	30	27	54	1733	3.40	65.27	9.90
24	1	31	23	23	1756	3.43	66.14	10.23
25	2	33	22	44	1800	3.50	67.80	10.89
26	1	34	21	21	1821	3.53	68.59	11.22
27	1	35	20	20	1841	3.56	69.34	11.55
28	1	36	19	19	1860	3.58	70.06	11.88
29	3	39	16	48	1908	3.66	71.86	12.87
30	5	44	15	75	1983	3.78	74.69	14.52
31	2	46	14	28	2011	3.83	75.74	15.18
32	3	49	13	39	2050	3.89	77.21	16.17
33	1	50	12	12	2062	3.91	77.66	16.50
34	2	52	11	22	2084	3.95	78.49	17.16
35	2	54	10	20	2104	3.99	79.25	17.82
36	3	57	9	27	2131	4.04	80.26	18.81
37	5	62	8	40	2171	4.13	81.77	20.46
38	6	68	7	42	2213	4.22	83.35	22.44
39	7	75	6	42	2255	4.32	84.93	24.75
40	7	82	5	35	2290	4.41	86.25	27.06
41	17	99	4	68	2358	4.60	88.81	32.67
42	20	119	3	60	2418	4.78	91.07	39.27
43	53	172	2	106	2524	5.15	95.07	56.77
44	131	303	1	131	2655	5.71	100.00	100.00

Table 3
Scatter of Journals and Citations over Bradford's zone

Zone	No. of Journals	% of Journals	No. of Citations	% of Citations	Bradford Multiplier
1	8	2.64	905	34.09	–
2	23	7.59	851	32.05	2.88
3	272	89.77	899	33.86	11.83
All Zones	303	100.00	2655	100.00	7.36*

Note: *Mean value of Bradford Multiplier

Therefore the following method, based on Leimkuhler model is applied for studying the applicability of Bradford's law.

5.2.2. Application of Leimkuhler model

For testing the Bradford's law, the 303 journal titles (ranked by their decreasing order of productivity) are divided in to three zones, since Bradford assumes that there should be minimum three zones. ie, when $p = 3$, then the value of k can be calculated using the formula (4)

$$k = (1.781 * Y_m)^{1/p} = (1.781 * 345)^{1/3} = 8.5$$

$$Y_0 = A/P = 2655/3 = 885$$

$$r_0 = T(k - 1)/(k^p - 1) = 303(8.5 - 1)/(8.5^3 - 1) \\ = 3.71$$

$$a = Y_0 / \log k = 885 / \log 8.5 = 952.20$$

$$b = k - 1/r_0 = 8.5 - 1/3.71 = 2.02$$

The findings of the calculations are shown in the Table 4.

From Table 4, the number of journals in the nucleus is found to be 4 and $k = 8.20$, is a multiplier. There fore the Bradford distribution is:

$$4 : 4 \times 8.20 : 4 \times 8.20^2 \approx 1 : n : n^2 \\ 4 : 32.8 : 268.8 \approx 305.6$$

$$\text{Percentage of error} = \frac{305.6 - 303}{303} \times 100 = 0.86\%$$

The percentage of error of the distribution is 0.86% and it is also observed that, the number of journals contributing the articles to each zone increases by a multiplier of 8.20. Specifically the first zone, containing 4 journals, contributes 646 articles, the second zone consisting 31 journals produces 1,110 articles, and the third zone accounting for 268 journals provides 899 articles.

Table 4
Bradford's zones of Scattering

Zone	No. of Journals	% of Journals	No. of Citations	% of Citations	Multiplication factor*
1	4	1.32	646	24.33	–
2	31	10.23	1110	41.81	7.75
3	268	88.45	899	33.86	8.65
All zone	303	100.00	2655	100.00	8.20

Note: *Estimated value of k in Bradford's law

The Bradford's algebraic interpretation of the law, $1 : n : n^2$ is followed in this case. But the number of articles in each zone doesn't follow the one third of the total citations.

In one of his articles, Cline [46] responded that 'such group of data which contains smaller percentage errors indicate a closer adherence to the Bradford distribution'. Accordingly, the Bradford's law almost fits well in this case.

The analysis shows that there are 4 core journals which cover 646 (24.33%) citations. These 4 journals are having heavy concentration of relevant articles in Physics referred by the researchers. The core journals may be taken as most authentic journals, which carry maximum information needs of the Physicists of University of Kerala. Thus a small number of journals (4) covers maximum of information needs, where as rest of about 75% of citations are collected from quite a large group (299) of journals.

5.2.3 Graphical Formulation

The graphical formulation is just the experimental verification of the verbal formulation which observes certain regularity in the distribution of scientific publications.

The graph in the Figure 1 is logarithmic plot of the cumulative number of journal titles on the horizontal axis and the cumulative number of citations on the vertical axis. If the distribution confirms to Bradford's law, the graph is known as 'Bradford Bibliograph' and it will display the characteristics of 3 distinct regions (i) a rapid rise for the first few points (ii) a major portion of linear relation between two variables and (iii) a 'droop' at the tail end of the distribution indicating the incompleteness of the bibliography (Brookes [42]).

$$R(n) = k \log(n/s)$$

$R(n)$ = The number of relevant papers contributed by journal ranked n .

k = is a constant which determines the slope of the Bradford's curve and is related to the document collection.

s = is a constant which determines where the straight line, if extended, would intersect the horizontal axis.

The Figure 1 shows the typical Bradford curve with a Groos droop, where the journals are plotted against their productivity.

Figure 1
Bradford's Bibliograph

According to Bradford, the area described by the curving line is usually regarded as nucleus zone or core journals and considered as the most productive zone: the area covered by the linear straight line is the moderately productive zone; and the area which is often called as the Groos Droop (or 'inflection point') represents the peripheral zone or outer zone, ie the least productive zone where relevant references are widely scattered among a great number of periodicals (Brookes [43]).

6. Conclusion

The journal distribution pattern of doctoral theses of the University of Kerala does not conform to the Bradford's distribution pattern, i.e., $1:n;n^2$, and it may be due to incomplete bibliography or interdisciplinary nature of articles. When the multiplier for the first two zones are calculated, the Bradford's law could be modified as $1:n;4n^2$ (where $n = 8$) and this modification confirms the Bradford law for the data set. But when the mean value of multiplier is considered (7.36), this modified Bradford law does not confirm the journal distribution, as the percentage of error is very high (65.09%). When the Leimkuhler model is employed for the verification of Bradford's law, it is found that the law is valid for the data set. The percentage of error is found to be most negligible (0.86%). But the number of articles in each zone doesn't follow the one third of the total citations.

The application of Bradford's law of scattering is an area where much work has been done. However, till now no one has come out with a single model that fits fairly well to most of the data set.

The list of journals will serve as a core list for researchers in Physics and academic librarians to use in future research and in collection development decisions. This study will be important to both Physicists and academic librarians because it is the first study to analyse journals used by the physicists in the University of Kerala. The Analysis of journal productivity has also been used as a tool for collection management in libraries by identifying core journals in subject area, thereby providing evidence for journal subscription decision making.

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